

Midfacial Trauma from Diverse Causes: A Unified Surgical Approach in Two Case Reports

Running Title: Reconstructive approach in facial trauma

Author details

Author 1 and corresponding author:

Dr.Ch. Laxman Roy*

Senior Lecturer, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial surgery, Mamata Dental college, Khammam- 507002

Author 2:

Dr.P.B.N. Mounika

MDS, Pediatric and Preventive Dentist, Sahasra ENT Superspeciality Hospital, Hyderabad

No. of words: 1658

No of pages: 5

No of references: 11

No of words in abstract: 237

Received: July 30, 2025

Accepted: Aug 29, 2025

Published: Aug 30, 2025

ABSTRACT:

Maxillofacial trauma is a significant concern in emergency and surgical practice due to the complex anatomy of the facial region and the vital functions it supports. The midface is particularly susceptible to traumatic injuries arising from road traffic accidents, interpersonal violence and occupational hazards. These injuries may result in facial disfigurement, functional impairment and psychological distress, necessitating prompt and precise intervention. This report presents two distinct cases of midfacial trauma with different etiologies but similar management goals. The first case involves a 35-year-old female who sustained a penetrating injury from an axe assault, resulting in a large midfacial laceration with exposure of the nasal cavity, maxillary bones and nasal cartilages. Imaging revealed naso-orbito-ethmoid (NOE) and infraorbital fractures. The second case describes a 25-year-old male involved in a road traffic accident, presenting with zygomaticomaxillary complex fracture, mandibular parasymphysis fracture and deranged occlusion. Both cases were managed surgically through open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using titanium plates and screws. Additional intraoral and extraoral incisions, as well as arch bar fixation, were employed to achieve stable occlusion and facial symmetry. Postoperative recovery was uneventful in both cases, with satisfactory healing and no functional deficits. These cases emphasize the importance of early diagnosis, multidisciplinary planning and individualized surgical intervention in managing facial trauma. Furthermore, they underscore the need for ongoing documentation and reporting of regional trauma patterns, which can guide clinical practice and contribute to improving outcomes in maxillofacial surgery.

Keywords: Midfacial Trauma, Zygomaticomaxillary Complex Fracture, Mandibular Fracture, Open Reduction and Internal Fixation (ORIF), Facial Injury Management

Introduction

Maxillofacial injuries, particularly those involving the zygomaticomaxillary complex (ZMC) and mandible are among the most frequently encountered facial fractures in trauma care. These injuries not only compromise facial aesthetics but also interfere with critical functions such as mastication, speech, vision and respiration. The anatomical prominence and biomechanical significance of the zygoma and mandible render them especially vulnerable to high-impact trauma, most commonly resulting from road traffic accidents (RTAs) and interpersonal violence [1,2].

The zygoma, a key contributor to midfacial contour and orbital integrity, is the most frequently involved bone in midface trauma, particularly in cases involving two-wheeler collisions [3]. Fractures of the ZMC can result in enophthalmos, diplopia, infraorbital nerve dysfunction and facial asymmetry if not appropriately treated [4]. Recent epidemiological studies across various regions in India consistently report mandibular fractures as the most prevalent maxillofacial injuries, with the parasymphysis and condylar regions being the most commonly affected sites.⁵ Mandibular fractures specially those involving the parasymphysis and angle can lead to malocclusion, temporomandibular joint dysfunction, and airway compromise [5]. Prompt diagnosis and anatomical reduction are essential to restore both function and aesthetics.

Surgical management using open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) remains the gold standard for displaced midfacial and mandibular fractures. Titanium plates and screws provide the rigidity necessary for early mobilization and predictable healing outcomes [6]. In selected cases, existing traumatic wounds may be utilized for surgical access, minimizing additional tissue disruption and scarring [7].

This report presents two distinct cases of facial trauma: one resulting from a penetrating injury (axe assault) and the other from a blunt force trauma (road traffic accident). Despite differing etiologies, both cases involved complex fractures requiring multidisciplinary management and surgical reconstruction.

Case Report 1:

A 35-year-old female patient presented to the emergency department following an assault with an axe. She experienced a brief loss of consciousness at the scene but regained consciousness during ambulance transport. On arrival, she was alert, oriented and reported no symptoms of nausea, vomiting, dizziness or disorientation. Her medical history was unremarkable, with no known drug allergies. On clinical examination, a deep facial laceration measuring approximately 10 × 3 cm was noted. The wound extended from the lateral canthus of the right eye, crossed the nasal bridge and reached the left oral commissure. The laceration exposed the nasal cavities, cartilages and underlying maxillary bone, with active bleeding observed. A computed tomography (CT) scan of the facial bones revealed a naso-orbito-ethmoidal (NOE) complex fracture, right infraorbital fracture and fracture of the anterior wall of the maxilla. There were no signs of intracranial involvement. Under general anesthesia, open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) were performed using titanium plates and screws, with surgical access obtained through the existing laceration. The NOE and infraorbital fractures were reduced and stabilized, and layered closure of the soft tissue was carried out to restore facial contour. Postoperatively, the patient recovered uneventfully, with no infraorbital sensory deficits noted. Facial aesthetics and symmetry were successfully restored, and the surgical site healed without complications.

Case Report 2:

A 25-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department following a road traffic accident involving a fall from a motorcycle. The patient remained conscious throughout and denied symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, dizziness or disorientation. His medical history was non-contributory, with no known drug allergies. Clinical examination revealed facial asymmetry with depression of the right malar region, mobility of mandibular segments and deranged occlusion. A computed tomography (CT) scan revealed a fracture of the right infraorbital rim extending posteriorly with displacement of the zygomatic arch, involving the dentoalveolar component in the region of tooth 14. Additionally, a parasymphysis fracture of the mandible was identified, extending from the region of teeth 32–33 to the lower border of the mandible. The patient was taken up for surgical management under general anesthesia. An extraoral approach was performed using an incision placed 1 cm below the subciliary margin in the infraorbital region, along with an intraoral vestibular incision to access the fracture sites. Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) were performed using titanium plates and screws. For mandibular stabilization and occlusal correction, arch bar fixation was carried out and planned to remain in place for 6 weeks. Layered wound closure was completed using 3-0 resorbable Vicryl sutures for intraoral

closure, and 3-0 Prolene with subcuticular suturing for extraoral closure. Postoperative healing was satisfactory, with stable occlusion, restored facial symmetry and no signs of infection or complications

Discussion:

Maxillofacial trauma continues to be a significant public health concern, particularly in developing countries where road traffic accidents (RTAs), interpersonal violence and occupational injuries are prevalent. The zygomaticomaxillary complex (ZMC) and mandible are among the most frequently affected regions due to their prominence and structural susceptibility. Injuries to these areas pose both functional and aesthetic challenges, affecting mastication, speech, vision, facial symmetry and overall quality of life.

The two cases presented—a penetrating facial injury caused by an axe assault and a blunt trauma sustained in a road traffic accident—illustrate the varied etiologies and fracture patterns commonly encountered in clinical settings [1,8].

Zygomatic and mandibular fractures frequently co-occur in high-impact injuries due to the anatomical prominence and structural vulnerabilities of these regions. The zygomaticomaxillary complex plays a pivotal role in midfacial support, orbital integrity and facial contour, while the parasymphysis of the mandible is particularly susceptible to fracture due to its thin cortical structure and the influence of surrounding musculature.

Both patients were managed with open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using titanium plates and screws, facilitating stable fixation and early functional recovery. The use of combined intraoral and extra oral surgical approaches provided enhanced access, enabling accurate anatomical reduction with minimal morbidity [9,10]. Notably, in the penetrating trauma case, the existing laceration was effectively utilized as a surgical access point, thereby minimizing additional soft tissue disruption and improving overall healing outcomes.

Rigid internal fixation ensured stability and promoted bone healing. Additionally, arch bar fixation played a key role in maintaining occlusal relationships in the mandibular fracture case. These cases underscore the importance of early diagnosis, meticulous surgical planning and a multidisciplinary approach in managing complex facial injuries. Reporting such diverse cases contributes to clinical learning, supports evidence-based practice and enhances the regional literature on trauma management [3,11].

Conclusion:

Maxillofacial trauma requires prompt evaluation and individualized surgical management to restore both form and function. The cases presented highlight the importance of adapting surgical approaches to the nature of the injury, utilizing existing wounds when feasible and employing rigid fixation techniques for optimal outcomes. Documenting such varied clinical scenarios enhances trauma care awareness and supports the continued evolution of maxillofacial surgical practice.

Patient Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying clinical images.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest

References:

1. Gassner R, Tuli T, Hächl O, Rudisch A, Ulmer H. Cranio-maxillofacial trauma: A 10-year review of 9,543 cases with 21,067 injuries. *J Craniomaxillofac Surg.* 2003;31(1):51–61.
2. Abdullah WA. Patterns of maxillofacial fractures in Riyadh city, Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Dent J.* 2013;25(1):33–38.
3. Kim YK, Kim SG, Yun PY, Kim JW. Surgical outcomes of ZMC complex fracture reduction using three-point fixation. *J Korean Assoc Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2011;37(6):453–458.
4. Boffano P, Roccia F, Zavatiero E, Dediol E, Uglešić V, Kovačić Ž, et al. Mandibular fractures: A 10-year multicenter retrospective study. *Craniomaxillofac Trauma Reconstr.* 2013;6(4):225–229.
5. Ravindran C, Vignesh R, Dinesh Kumar R. Zygomatic complex fractures: A clinical and radiographic study. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg Med Pathol.* 2019
6. Al-Moraissi EA, El-Sharkawy TM, Mounair RM, El-Ghareeb TI. Three-dimensional versus standard miniplate fixation in the management of mandibular fractures: A meta-analysis. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2014;43(7):847–854.
7. Kaura S, Singh P, Bansal N, Bhatia N. Use of existing wounds as surgical access in maxillofacial trauma: An innovative approach. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg.* 2019;10(1):97–100.
8. Motamedi MH. An assessment of maxillofacial fractures: A 5-year study of 237 patients. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2003;61(1):61–64.
9. Roccia F, Boffano P, Crimi S, et al. Management of facial trauma in a tertiary center: A 10-year review. *J Stomatol Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2017;118(4):185–190.
10. Ellis E 3rd, Zide MF. *Surgical Approaches to the Facial Skeleton.* 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2006.
11. Al Ahmed HE, Jaber MA, Abu Fanas SH, Karas M. The pattern of maxillofacial fractures in Sharjah, United Arab Emirates: A review of 230 cases. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 2004;98(2):166–170.